

NFDI4Energy Conference

1. NFDI4Energy Conference

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Doing What is the Best: Best Practices in Energy Research

A Structured Literature Review

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1 Motivation

In energy research, following agreed-upon guidelines or best practices is crucial for achieving optimal results. These guidelines help to consolidate research, save time by making data and software reusable, and make research more comparable. For this work, a definition adapted from business process management (BPM) and software engineering is used as a base for structured exploration of the topic. In detail, the definition is adapted from Reijers and Liman Mansar [1] and Wagner, Scott, and Galliers [2]. Best practices can be understood as practices and generally agreed-upon standards that increase the possibility of a positive outcome when followed. Unlike BPM and software engineering, there is no agreed-upon definition or procedure for recording best practices in energy research. Additionally, there is no registry to easily find best practices for different topics and they exist in multiple media formats.

The NFDI4Energy platform aims to catalog existing best practices and enable researchers to record new ones to assist them in their daily professional lives. It is essential to review existing best practices to conceptualize an appropriate corresponding service on the right platform for gathering them. To our best knowledge, there is no existing literature review regarding best practices in energy research. Therefore, we will conduct a structured literature review. Literature reviews are an important research tool to collect, structure, and analyze existing knowledge in science making them an appropriate research approach for our planned examination [3]–[5].

The contributions of the literature review will be twofold: First, the extracted best practices will be used to conceptualize the best practice module for the NFDI4Energy platform and serve as a foundation for first mock-ups. Second, the found results will be used as the first content for the platform element. This abstract shows our approach to designing the best practice module with a focus on the literature review. The aim of this abstract is to get feedback about our methodology and preliminary observations from the attendants of the NFDI4Energy conference.

2 Methodology

2.1 Structured Literature Review

For building an accurate and useful best practice module, it is essential to get an overview of the state of the art in scientific research and a scope of the amount of best practices available. Since there is no existing literature review available for best practices in energy research, it is determined that conducting a literature review is the first step in analyzing what best practices currently exist in this field. This review is categorized as a scoping review as the aims of the review fit the following definition by Paré, Trudel, Jaana, *et al.* [4]:

scoping reviews attempt to provide an initial indication of the potential size and nature of the available literature on a particular topic.

The Prisma approach was chosen as a procedure to display the review process, as it is an established research process when conducting literature reviews [6]. While general practices in research, such as conventions concerning citations, are applicable to energy research and best practices in formats like videos exist, a strong topical focus on energy research is desired for this review. As such the search is limited to scientific literature concerning best practices in energy research. To reflect this, the search term is limited to *"best practice" AND "energy research"*. It is applied to the title, abstract and keywords fields of the search databases. The search is modified for the differently named search fields of the databases as necessary.

To provide an extensive overview we chose the following databases: IEEE Xplore¹, ScienceDirect², MDPI³ and AiSeL⁴. Excluded from the search are books, chapters, conference papers, and editorials. No time frame is set for the search as the scope of the search is limited and only English literature is considered. The data acquired from the literature review will be collected and openly made available to other researchers.

2.2 Module Conceptualization

The data acquired from the literature review will be used in two ways. Firstly, the data itself will be utilized as material for the best practice module of the platform. Secondly, it will be employed to refine a good way of formulating best practices, which will serve as the foundation for the subsequent conceptualization.. Following this, feature-driven development (FDD) methodology, as suggested by Palmer and Felsing [7], will be utilized. This involves extracting features from the concept and using them to develop the module by feature.

3 Preliminary Discussions and Conclusions

This abstract presents the planned methodology for creating a best practice module on the NFDI4Energy platform. The goal of this abstract is to solicit feedback on the proposed approach. The planned methodology is explained based on a Best practice definition and a literature review is planned. A preliminary unstructured review suggests that there is relevant literature available on this topic, such as Amorim [8] who gathered best practices for energy research platforms or Agrawal, De Tommasi, Lyons,

¹See: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/Xplore/home.jsp>

²See: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/>

³See: <https://www.mdpi.com/>

⁴See: <https://aisel.aisnet.org/>

et al. [9] who provided guidelines for increasing energy efficiency in small and medium-sized businesses. Another example is GARCÍA [10] who highlighted best practices in grid-connected renewable energy and discussed how policies in China were conflicting with them. We believe that a structured literature review will provide us with a more comprehensive understanding of the current state of best practices in energy research, which we can then use to develop a module for our platform.

Author contributions

Alexandro Steinert: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing- Original draft preparation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing, Investigation. Oliver Werth: Writing- Reviewing and Editing, Investigation. Astrid Nieße: Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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